

Kinetic studies on the reduction of dithiazone by sulphite ions in micellar media

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Abstract : This study reveals the micellar effects on the rate of reduction of dithiazone, an azo compound by sulphite ions in a buffer medium of pH 7. The reduction of dithiazone was studied in absence and presence of micellar forming surfactants, Cetyl Trimethyl Ammonium Bromide (CTAB) and Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate (SDS). A 0.1 M cationic surfactant CTAB catalyses the reaction and increases the rate by five times whereas the same concentration of an anionic micelle SDS has completely inhibited the reduction reaction. The significant rate enhancement of this reaction in presence of CTAB micelles is due to the hydrophobic and electrostatic interactions between the substrate, reductant and micelles. The binding constant between the substrate and CTAB micelles has been found to be 329.3 M⁻¹.

Keywords : Micellar media, dithiazone, sulphite ion.

Kinetic studies on the reduction of organic compounds by sulphite ions, has not been focused much when compared to the kinetics of reduction of inorganic compounds¹. Analytical applications of azo dyes are many^{2,3}. Many reducing agents can bring about the reduction of azo compounds like hydrazine, titanous chloride, lithium aluminium hydride, sodium sulphite^{4,5}, etc. The kinetic studies on reduction of azo dyes was studied by Ogawa *et al.* and found that SnCl₂ reduces compounds directly to amines but sodium sulphite reduces them to hydrazo derivatives and then gradually to amines⁶. Micelle forming surfactants in aqueous medium have been found to cause significant rate enhancements and inhibitions of several organic and inorganic reactions^{7,8}. Micelles equilibrate rapidly with monomeric surfactant and hydrophobic solutes, and are partitioned between bulk solvent and the micelles. Hence the reactions may occur at higher rates in micelles than in bulk solvent⁹. We have therefore, attempted to explore the use of micellar media for the reduction of azo compounds by sulphite ions. The paper deals with the kinetics of reduction of dithiazone by sulphite ions (SO₃²⁻) in micelles of Cetyl Trimethyl Ammonium Bromide (CTAB) and Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate (SDS).

Results and discussion

Kinetic studies in the absence of surfactants :

Reduction of dithiazone by SO₃²⁻ was done in medium of phosphate buffer of pH 7.0. The reaction was carried out under first order conditions keeping the concentration of sulphite ions much greater than that of dithiazone, which are given by the linear plots of log abs. vs time. The change in absorbance with time was noted at 603.5 nm. The dependence of rate of reduction on the substrate concentration was examined by monitoring the kinetic runs at varying dithiazone in the range 2.0 × 10⁻³ – 8.0 × 10⁻³ M (Table 1).

The dependence of rate of reduction on the SO₃²⁻ concentration was examined by monitoring the kinetic runs at varying SO₃²⁻ in the range 1.0 × 10⁻² – 3.0 × 10⁻² M. The rate of the reaction increases as the SO₃²⁻ concentration increases and shows that the reaction is first order with respect to SO₃²⁻ (Table 1). Effect of ionic strength on the rate of reduction of dithiazone by SO₃²⁻ was studied by varying the concentration of NaCl. In the absence of surfactant increase in [NaCl] has negligible effect on the rate. Dependence of the rate of reduction of dithiazone on [H⁺] was examined in the pH range of 4.0–10.0 (Fig. 3). The rate of the reaction increased with the increase in pH upto 7.0 (Table 1).

Table 1. Effect of dithiazone, SO_3^{2-} and Cl^- concentrations and pH on the rate of reduction of dithiazone by SO_3^{2-} at 28 °C

pH=7.0, $[\text{SO}_3^{2-}] = 1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$, $[\text{dithiazone}] = 6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$

[Dithiazone] $\times 10^4 \text{ (M)}$	$k \times 10^3$ (s^{-1})	$[\text{SO}_3^{2-}] \times 10^2$ (M)	$k \times 10^3$ (s^{-1})	$[\text{Cl}^-]$ (M)	$k \times 10^3$ (s^{-1})	pH	$k \times 10^4$ (s^{-1})
2.0	1.92	1.0	1.919	0.01	1.73	4.0	2.19
3.0	1.855	1.5	2.1	0.02	1.57	6.0	6.91
4.0	1.974	2.0	3.7	0.03	1.77	7.0	9.59
5.0	1.87	2.5	4.2			10.0	6.14
6.0	1.919	3.0	5.8			11.5	4.0
7.0	2.047						
8.0	1.727						

Table 2. Effect of dithiazone, SO_3^{2-} and Cl^- concentrations and pH on the rate of reduction of dithiazone by SO_3^{2-} in the presence of 0.1 M CTAB at 28 °C

pH = 7.0, $[\text{SO}_3^{2-}] = 1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$, $[\text{dithiazone}] = 6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$

[Dithiazone] $\times 10^4 \text{ (M)}$	$k \times 10^3$ (s^{-1})	$[\text{SO}_3^{2-}] \times 10^2$ (M)	$k \times 10^3$ (s^{-1})	$[\text{Cl}^-]$ (M)	$k \times 10^3$ (s^{-1})	pH	$k \times 10^4$ (s^{-1})
1.0	7.1	1.0	8.4	0.5	3.6	5.17	1.1
2.0	6.8	1.5	9.5	1.0	3.2	5.67	1.5
3.0	8.0	2.0	16.2	1.5	2.8	6.5	1.8
4.0	7.3	2.5	18.5	2.0	2.3	7.0	4.79
5.0	6.5	3.0	24.4	2.5	2.0	7.6	2.6
6.0	8.4					10.0	1.7

Kinetic studies in the presence of surfactants :

The reduction of dithiazone by SO_3^{2-} was studied in the presence of cationic surfactant CTAB and anionic surfactant SDS in phosphate buffer. Kinetic studies were made under first order conditions by keeping $[\text{SO}_3^{2-}]$ very high (~ 1000 times) than dithiazone.

The effect of concentrations of dithiazone, SO_3^{2-} and pH on the rate of reduction of dithiazone by SO_3^{2-} was studied in the presence of 0.1 M CTAB (Table 2). Increase in SO_3^{2-} increased the rate linearly in the presence of CTAB, indicating first order dependence on SO_3^{2-} also. Effect of ionic strength was found to be very negligible in the absence of micelles, whereas it had a decreasing effect in the presence of micelles (Fig. 1). Effect of cationic micelles on the rate of reduction of dithiazone by SO_3^{2-} was studied by varying the CTAB concentration in the range 1×10^{-5} - 0.1 M (Fig. 2). The effect of anionic surfactant SDS on the rate of reduction of dithiazone by SO_3^{2-} was investigated by varying the SDS concentration in the range 1.0×10^{-5} - 1.0×10^{-2} M. From 1.0×10^{-4} M concentration of SDS, the reaction is completely inhibited. Under experimental conditions the observed rate law may be given as

Fig. 1. Effect of added $[\text{NaCl}]$ on the rate of reduction of dithiazone in (a) absence and (b) presence of NaCl .

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{dithiazone}] = k[\text{S}] [\text{SO}_3^{2-}] \quad (1)$$

On the basis of Scheme 1, the rate of disappearance of dithiazone is given by

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 [\text{S}] [\text{SO}_3^{2-}] + k_2 [\text{SH}^+] [\text{SO}_3^{2-}] \quad (2)$$

The total concentration of the substrate can be expressed as

Fig. 2. Effect of pH on the rate of reduction of dithiazone in (a) absence and (b) presence of CTAB.

$$[S_T] = [S] [SH^+] \quad (3)$$

The concentration of S and SH⁺ can be written in terms of S_T and the protonation constant (K_p)

$$[S] = \frac{[S_T]}{1 + K_p [H^+]} \quad (4)$$

$$[SH^+] = \frac{[S_T] K_p [H^+]}{1 + K_p [H^+]} \quad (5)$$

Substituting for [SH⁺] and [S] in eq. (2), the rate if the reaction can be expressed as

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_1 + k_2 K_p [H^+]}{1 + K_p [H^+]} [S_T] [SO_3^{2-}] \quad (6)$$

The observed rate law is consistent with the rate equation. Hence on comparing eq. (6) and eq. (2), it yields,

$$k' = \frac{k_1 + k_2 K_p [H^+]}{1 + K_p [H^+]} \quad (7)$$

Eq. (7) explains the rate dependence on H⁺. The decrease in the rate with increase in the concentration of H⁺ till pH 7.0 indicates that the reaction proceeds predominantly through the path involving S in this pH range (Scheme 1).

The following mechanism is proposed in support of the experimental results.

The above mechanism leads to the rate law as follows for the disappearance of the dithiazone.

$$\frac{-d [\text{dithiazone}]}{dt} = \{k_1 K_p [H^+] + k_2\} [S] [SO_3^{2-}]$$

Effect of cationic surfactant : The rate of catalytic reduction of CTAB micelles (at 0.1 M) was found to be 5 times higher than without CTAB. The substrate induced micellisation¹⁰ or formation of pre-micellar aggregates are

formed since catalysis takes place well below the reported CMC of CTAB (9.2×10^{-4} M). The concentration effect of CTAB on the rate of reduction at pH 7 is shown in the Fig. 2.

This catalytic effect can be understood on the basis of electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions between micelles of CTAB, dithiazone and SO₃²⁻. Hydrophobicity of dithiazone is responsible for its incorporation into the micellar pseudophase. This can also be the reason for inhibition as well. The concentration SO₃²⁻ at the micellar surface will be more than that in the bulk phase due to electrostatic interactions between SO₃²⁻ and CTAB micelles. Enhanced concentration of both dithiazone and SO₃²⁻ at the micellar interface leads to catalysis of reaction.

The above argument can be supported by the fact that increase in added [Cl⁻], shows inhibitory effect of CTAB catalyzed reaction than in non-micellar medium (Fig. 1). As [Cl⁻] is increased, exchange of added counter ions with those already present at the micellar surface takes place¹¹. This leads to the decrease in the SO₃²⁻ at the micellar surface. Hence, the rate of CTAB catalyzed reaction decreases.

Effect of pH on the CTAB catalysed reduction of dithiazone by SO₃²⁻ was studied which showed that the pH increased to a maximum and then decreased (Fig. 2). To study the effect of added counter ions on the CTAB catalysed reaction, kinetic runs were performed by varying the concentration of NaCl in the range 0.005 to 0.025 M. The proposed mechanism (Scheme 1) is with two paths, one involving the protonated substrate and other involving unprotonated substrate, is consistent with this interesting observation. Due to electrostatic attraction between SH⁺ and CTAB micelles, binding them is more favorable than between substrate (S) and CTAB micelles. Catalysis must be probably due to the reaction proceeding predominantly in micellar phase and the step involving S mainly contributing to the observed rate. The variation of observed first order rate constant (k_ψ) according to Menger and Portnoy¹², is given by

$$K_\psi = \frac{k_w + k_m K_s (C_d - \text{CMC})}{1 + K_s (C_d - \text{CMC})} \quad (1)$$

In the above equation k_w and k_m are the first order rate constants in aqueous and micellar phases, respectively. The observed rate constant K_ψ, can be analysed on the

basis of Piszkwicz's model for the micellar catalysed reaction, testing the catalytic effect of CTAB on the reduction of dithiazone.

His scheme is outlined below :

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

The protonated substrate in aqueous phase is in equilibrium with $D_n^{1,1}SH^+$ (in micellar phase). D_n and $D_n^{1,1}$ are micellised surfactants. D_nS catalytic micelles are formed due to the aggregation of substrate S and a number of 'n' detergent molecules. Under experimental condition due to pH, ionic strength and SO_3^{2-} , Scheme 2 gives rise to expression (2)

$$\frac{K_\psi - k_w}{k_m - K_\psi} = K_s (C_d - CMC) \quad (2)$$

As per eq. (2), k_w is the rate constant in aqueous phase, K_s is micelle-substrate binding constant expressed in terms of micellised surfactant and C_D is the detergent concentration. A plot of $(k_\psi - k_w)/k_m - k_\psi$ vs C_D is found to be

Fig. 3. Variation of rate constant with CTAB concentration for the reduction of dithiazone by sulphite ions.

Fig. 4. Analysis of the effect of CTAB on the rate of reduction of dithiazone.

linear (Fig. 4). K_s value obtained from the plots for the reduction of dithiazone was 329.3 M^{-1} . This value indicates significant binding between dithiazone and CTAB micelles. Raghavan and Sreenivasan¹³ justify the model given in Scheme 2 to the bimolecular reaction under investigation considering the arguments put forward. The proposal given by them was a kinetic model for bimolecular reactions considering distribution of both reactant and nucleophile in aqueous and micellar phases.

The product is assumed to result from the decomposition of complex involving substrate, nucleophile and micelle. On the basis of this model the data was analyzed and concluded that, all the nucleophile is present in the bulk phase, which is an irony to the assumption of Romsted¹⁴ as well as Reeve¹⁵. Their assumption was that in cases, where nucleophile resides predominantly in Stern layer of the micelle, Menger and Portnoy treatment for unimolecular reaction should hold good for bimolecular reaction.

Effect of anionic surfactant :

Anionic micelles of SDS have complete inhibitory effect. This may be due to SH^+ binding to SDS micelles. Both electrostatic and hydrophobic forces favors binding but SO_3^{2-} approaches to the micelle bound SH^+ where electrostatic repulsions become favorable. The observed rate in the presence of very low SDS concentration may be due to the small reaction-taking place in aqueous phase.

Results given based on this study demonstrated micelle substrate interactions are specific and depend on both electrostatic and hydrophobic forces. The investigation suggests that reduction of azo compounds by SO_3^{2-} can be carried out faster at pH 7 by using cationic micelles. Finding of these studies are expected to enhance the utility of micellar media for preparative and analytical purposes. These catalytic effects of micelles on the redox reactions of azo compounds helps in the develop-

ment of several methods to reduce the pollution in waste waters of industries dealing with azo dyes and nitroso compounds¹⁶. By doing so, azo compounds without any additives can reduce the pollution.

Experimental

Dithiazone (an azo derivative), sodium sulphite, acetic acid, sodium acetate, disodium hydrogen phosphate and sodium dihydrogen phosphate were of A.R. grade. SDS and CTAB were crystallized^{17,18}. All the solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water. The reaction was initiated by adding requisite quantity of sodium sulphite solution to a solution containing the azo compound and other reagents. The reaction was followed spectrophotometrically (Shimadzu 160) by observing decrease in absorbance of dithiazone at 603.5 nm with time. Ionic strength showed no effect on the rate of the reaction with sodium chloride in the absence of micelles and decreasing effect in presence of micelles. All the kinetic runs were recorded at the room temperature. Calculations and analysis of the kinetic data were carried out using a computer. The product identified was an amine by IR spectra.

References

1. C. R. Dennis, S. S. Basson and J. G. Leipoldt, *Polyhedron*, 1983, **2**, 1357.
2. R. M. Isa, A. K. Ghonium, H. A. Dessouk and H. M. Mustafa, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 286.
3. S. Lurieju, "Hand Book of Analytical Chemistry", Mir Publishers, Moscow, 1367, 196.
4. H. C. Brown and P. M. Weissman, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 5614.
5. H. C. Brown, P. M. Weissman and N. M. Yoon, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 1458.
6. T. Ogawa, K. Shibata, C. Yotome and Y. Takase, *Kogyo Kagakuzasshi*, 1971, **74**, 720.
7. E. J. Fendler and J. H. Fendler, *Adv. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 27.
8. E. H. Cordes and R. B. Dunlop, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1969, **2**, 329.
9. C. A. Bunton, *Prog. Solid Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 239; "Micellar Reactions. Chap. IV. Application of Biomedical Systems in Chemistry", Part II, ed. J. Bryan Jones, Wiley, New York, 1976.
10. D. Piszkiwicz, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **99**, 1550.
11. N. Funasaki, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1979, **83**, 1989.
12. F. M. Menger and C. E. Portnoy, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 4698.
13. P. S. Raghavan and V. S. Srinivasan, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1987, **98**, 199.
14. L. S. Romsted, "Micellisation, Solubilisation and Microemulsions", Vol. 2, ed. K. L. Mittal, Plenum Press, New York, 1977.
15. R. L. Reeves, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **97**, 6019, 6025.
16. N. C. Sarada and I. Ajit Kumar Reddy, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **83**, 135.
17. J. H. Cho and H. Morawetz, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 375.
18. Duynstee and E. Grunwald, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 4540.